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CORPORATE GOVERNANCE: THE CONCEPT AND THE MAIN APPROACHES TO ITS DEFINITION IN RUSSIA

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Abstract: The necessity of normative attaching to corporate management's definition is specified. A wide quantity of opinions concerning the maintenance of the essential elements making the concept «corporate management» is analyzed. It is stated that the acceptance of the unified approach to the maintenance of the concept «corporate management» is necessary at the present stage of development of the Russian corporate practice. The new definition of the investigated concept according to which corporate management represents the system of mutual relations among proprietors of the company, management and other privies concerning the following: maintenance of their interests through fair and equal rights in distribution of activity's results; the proprietors' monitoring of the company management; increasing of efficiency of the company and increasing in its profit; correspondence to social interests is offered.

Keywords: corporate management, system of the reporting, the company (the organization, the enterprise, firm).

Аннотация: Указывается на необходимость нормативного закрепления определения корпоративного управления. Проанализировано большое количество мнений относительно

содержания существенных элементов, составляющих понятие «корпоративный менеджмент». Утверждается, что принятие единого подхода к содержанию понятия «корпоративное управление» необходимо на современном этапе развития российской корпоративной практики. Дано новое определение исследуемого понятия, согласно которому корпоративное управление представляет собой систему взаимоотношений между собственниками компании, менеджментом и другими частными лицами по следующим вопросам: обеспечение их интересов посредством справедливого и равноправного распределения результатов деятельности; контроль собственников за управлением компанией; повышение эффективности развития компании и увеличения ее прибыли; предлагается соответствие социальным интересам.

Ключевые слова: корпоративное управление, система отчетности, компания (организация, предприятие, фирма).

Annotatsiya. korporativ boshqaruv ta'rifini tartibga soluvchi konsolidasiya qilish zarurati ta'kidlangan. "Korporativ menejment" tushunchasini tashkil etuvchi muhim elementlarning mazmuni to'g'risida ko'plab fikrlar tahlil qilindi. Ta'kidlanishicha, "korporativ boshqaruv" konsepsiyasining mazmuniga yagona yondashuvni qabul qilish Rossiya korporativ amaliyotining hozirgi rivojlanish bosqichida zarurdir. O'rganilayotgan konsepsiyaning yangi ta'rifi berilgan bo'lib, unga ko'ra korporativ boshqaruv - bu kompaniya egalari, menejment va boshqa shaxslar o'rtasidagi quyidagi masalalar bo'yicha munosabatlar tizimi: biznes natijalarini adolatli va adolatli taqsimlash orqali ularning manfaatlarini ta'minlash; mulkdorlarning kompaniya boshqaruvi ustidan nazorati; kompaniyaning rivojlanish samaradorligini oshirish va uning foydasini oshirish; ijtimoiy manfaatlarga rioya qilish taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: korporativ boshqaruv, hisobot tizimi, kompaniya (tashkilot, korxon, firma).

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The term "corporate governance" has often been used by government officials, business representatives, and journalists. However, currently there is no unified

approach to the definition of the concept of "corporate governance", and there is no definition of this concept in any regulatory legal act of Russia. The very term

"corporate governance" was first used by American economists. As the corporate practice develops, in an international legal act approved in April 1999. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development has formulated the following definition of corporate governance: "Corporate governance refers to the internal means of ensuring the activities of corporations and control over them... One of the key elements for improving economic efficiency is corporate governance, which includes a set of relationships between the management board (management, administration) of the company, its board of directors (supervisory board), shareholders and other stakeholders. Corporate governance also defines the mechanisms by which the company's goals are formulated, the means of achieving them and controlling its activities is determined" [1].

In Russia, the term "corporate governance" at the state level was first defined by the executive authority - financial markets in the publication "Corporate Governance: History and Practice" [2], which provides the following definitions of this concept:

- Corporate governance is a system of reporting to shareholders of persons who are entrusted with the current management of the company;

- Corporate governance is a way of managing a company that ensures a fair and equitable distribution of business results among all shareholders, as well as other

stakeholders;

- Corporate governance is a set of measures and rules that help shareholders control the company's management and influence management in order to maximize its profits and value;

- Corporate governance is a system of relationships between the managers of a company and its owners in matters of ensuring the effectiveness of its activities and protecting the interests of the owners, as well as other stakeholders.

The above definitions certainly reflect the essence of corporate governance, which consists in the separation of ownership and executive management, when the owner cannot directly control management decisions.

Modern researchers provide a number of definitions of the term "corporate governance", which include one or another additional aspect of the basic principle embedded in the traditional understanding of corporate governance.

Specialists of the Russian Institute of Directors I.Belikov and V.Verbitsky consider corporate governance as "a system of relationships between the owners (shareholders) of a company and its management, between various groups (categories) of shareholders, between the company as a whole and other stakeholders in matters of ensuring the interests of these participants in corporate relations and the effective operation of the company, its compliance social goals and public interests" [3, p. 117].

The designation of compliance of company management activities with social goals and public interests gives special relevance to this definition. The study of the social responsibility of Russian companies is currently a separate area of activity of unions and associations of entrepreneurs, and special attention is paid to the social responsibility of companies by the state.

The systemic nature of corporate governance is outlined in the work of M.M.Solovyov "Automated systems, management and corporate governance: the logic of separation and development" [4]. By now, in the theory and practice of management, there is a clear separation of management systems: automatic regulation (control system), management (management) and corporate governance (corporate governance). It was the widespread development of the stock market, the introduction of new standards in enterprise management, and the creation of multinational organizations that led to the formation of a new level of governance - the corporate governance system. For the corporate governance system, the management space has expanded significantly in comparison with the management system. It has become necessary to include, along with the managed company and indicators of its core market of goods and services, related markets and the stock market with information about a wide range of companies of potential interest in terms of

possible capital flows, structural interactions and transformations. However, in the corporate governance system, the company's functioning is provided by management, and the production of goods and services is provided by an automated management system. Thus, according to M.M.Solovyov, corporate governance is a management system that has emerged as a result of the transformation and development of the management system and the automated management system, which includes elements of these systems and is aimed at achieving consistency of interests of the company's owners and others through the prism of reliable and objective functioning of the company's top management.

O.A.Makarova defines the concept of "corporate governance" through definitions fixed in Russian legislation, emphasizing that corporate governance "is, first of all, management carried out on the basis of the law and internal documents of the corporation adopted in accordance with the law" [5, p. 26]. Of course, legal regulation plays a key role in the corporate governance of the company. O.A.Makarova, analyzing Article 53 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, which defines the concept of a legal entity, as well as the Law of December 26, 1995. No. 208-FZ "On Joint-Stock Companies", defines the concept of corporate governance in a narrow sense, "as an impact on a corporation as an organized system carried out by specially formed

bodies acting within their competence" [5, p. 26]. In our opinion, such a definition does not reflect the actual specifics of corporate governance, since there is no definition of the range of corporate entities, and the formation of bodies operating within their competence is typical for any organizations of various organizational and legal forms. In a broad sense, corporate governance, according to O.A.Makarova, is "the relationship within a corporation and its relationship with the outside world," i.e., "a system of relations between management bodies and owners of securities of the corporation (shareholders, owners of bonds and other securities), between the corporation and government agencies, as well as other stakeholders." persons involved in the management of the issuer (company) in one way or another as a legal entity" [5, p. 27].

The normative approach to the definition of the concept of "corporate governance" is noted by V.V.Dolinskaya. In her opinion, corporate governance is a system of organizational and property relations regulated by law, through which a corporate organization implements, represents and protects the interests of investors, and primarily shareholders [6, pp. 420-421].

S.D.Mogilevsky, based on data from various branches of modern science, concludes: "Corporate governance carried out by an economic society, being a type of social management, represents a continuous and purposeful regulating effect

on the behavior of people involved in the sphere of activity of an economic society (persons authorized to do so by law and constituent documents), in the range of corporate interests (participants, members of management bodies) or related to labor relations (employees and officials). This impact is realized through the managerial relations of the subject and the object of corporate governance formed between these persons" [7, p. 161].

According to A.Kilyachkov, corporate governance is a set of measures implemented by both foreign and Russian companies to protect the interests of owners and ultimately to increase the value of the company and attract investment [8, p. 51]. L.Z.Shneidman also notes that a proper corporate governance system allows owners to be confident that their funds are reasonably used by the management of the joint-stock company for the development of financial and economic activities [9, p. 16]. Schneidman notes that corporate governance in general is "a system of accountability to shareholders of persons entrusted with the current management of a joint-stock company," while corporate governance differs from the management of a joint-stock company, which, in turn, is more "operational activities and is carried out by executive bodies and officials."

V.Kleiner excludes the term "shareholders" from the definition of "corporate governance" as a generalizing name for the company's partners in the

stock market, and suggests using the concept of "investors", arguing that "investors are economic entities that are either already shareholders of the company (real shareholders, or just shareholders), or may become such in the future (potential shareholders) [8, p. 36]. As stockholders constantly migrate from the category of stockholders to the category of potential investors and back again, the company's relationship with shareholders turns into a relationship with investors - both those who are currently investors and those who may potentially become them. The use of the term "investors" in the definition of "corporate governance" is appropriate in the case of understanding the actual investors in the company's capital, be they institutional and portfolio investors. However, potential investors do not fall under the management action of the corporation, since they are not recognized as such in accordance with the procedure established by law and therefore cannot have certain rights and obligations possessed by actual shareholders involved in the management of the enterprise using these rights.

V. Kleiner believes that when forming the concept of "corporate governance" it is necessary to take into account the direct actors of the stock market, such as brokers, consultants, analysts, auditing companies, rating agencies. Of course, the above-mentioned entities have a strong influence on the formation of corporate strategy and the activities of the company's governing

bodies. Successful research results from rating agencies can help increase the company's capital by attracting new investors.

Defining the relationship between a corporation and the stock market, there are two main types of relationships:

- management flows or decision flows directed from shareholders to the company;
- information and financial flows directed in both directions.

The identification of such types of relationships between an enterprise and the stock market is based primarily on the totality of powers defined in legislation. At the same time, management decisions on the part of shareholders represent the hiring of the company's management, the formation of the board of directors, the selection of an auditor, etc. Information flows from the stock market to the company reflect the estimates and expectations of the market regarding the results of its activities. The information flow from the company to the stock market is designed not only to satisfy the management and control requests of the company's owners, but also to respond to information requests from investors and generate positive expectations from the company's activities. Thus, according to V. Kleiner, corporate governance is understood as "a system of relations between a public company and the stock market that determines:

- a) the managerial impact of shareholders and their groups on the

company.;

b) financial flows between the company and the stock market;

c) information flows between the company and the stock market" [10, p. 37].

The Soviet Encyclopedic dictionary defines management as an element, a function of organized systems of various natures (biological, social, technical), ensuring the preservation of their specific structure, maintaining the mode of activity, and implementing their programs and goals [11, p. 1400].

In the dictionary of S.I.Ozhegov, the concept of "corporate" is defined as "narrow-group, closed within the corporation" [12, p. 381].

Corporate governance is carried out in companies that are recognized by corporations due to economic, legal, socio-social criteria, and in this sense, corporate governance is a special type of management activity in companies with a joint-stock form of ownership. Corporate governance is a conscious management that is carried out by bodies specially formed in the corporation. These bodies are established in accordance with the procedure established by law, and have different competencies, the differentiation of which is carried out within the framework of the law. Therefore, corporate governance is the management carried out on the basis of the law and other regulatory legal acts. The regulatory regulation of corporate governance is one of its features and is designed to regulate, within the

framework of the law, the relationships that develop between management entities.

According to A.Osinovsky, all participants in corporate governance are divided into two groups: the joint-stock company itself and the shareholders of this company - the management of the corporation (issuer), large shareholders (majority), minority shareholders (holding a small number of shares), owners of the issuer's securities, creditors and partners who are not owners of the issuer's securities, federal executive authorities, executive authorities of the subjects of the Russian Federation, as well as local self-government bodies [13, pp. 20-22]. It is the regulation of relations between corporate governance entities aimed at ensuring the interests of participants in order to increase the efficiency of the company's activities that is the essence of corporate governance.

Thus, S.Masyutin believes that when regulating the relations of corporate governance entities, management always has two tasks: not to lose old shareholders, who may begin to get rid of the company's shares that do not generate income, and to attract new shareholders by placing additional shares [14, p. 93]. Of course, achieving this goal is to increase production efficiency and increase profits under corporate governance. - it should be implemented through a system of mechanisms, namely equity management, taking into account the interests of minority and majority shareholders, other stakeholders, interaction with professional

stock market participants on the movement of issued shares based on financial flows between the company and the stock market, the development of a culture of interaction with the internal and external business environment, implemented including through social responsibility of the company, its compliance with social goals and public interests. All the mechanisms and processes taking place in the corporation are structured and subject to strict regulation by law and internal regulations. Therefore, the relationships

that arise in the process of corporate governance are systemic in nature.

Thus, corporate governance is a system of relationships between the owners of a company, management and other stakeholders on issues of ensuring their interests through a fair and equitable distribution of business results, control by the owners of the company over its management and compliance with socio-public interests.

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